

TWIN TUBE DESIGN AND ANALYSIS USING ROCSCIENCE (PHASE 2.0) SOFTWARE**Mr. Vijay Ingole^{1,a*}, Dr. Amol B. Saner^{2,b}**¹M.E. Student, Matoshri College of Engineering and Research Centre, Nashik²Head of Department, Matoshri College of Engineering and Research Centre, Nashik

Abstract. The report provides a comprehensive overview of the tunnel design process, which involves ensuring the strength of support structures, grading rock types, selecting the characteristics of exceptional tunnels, and comprehending the terrain. By examining these important factors, the report will provide a better understanding of the complexities associated with tunnel design in various geographic environments. The evolution of the tunnel's construction is also shown, from the start of excavations to its current role in facilitating new transport networks. Emphasizing the importance of safety, durability and innovation, the report outlines the key considerations needed to build fit-for-purpose tunnels.

Keywords: Empirical Methods, Rock Classification, Support System, Tunnel design and Tunnel Geometry

I. INTRODUCTION

The tunnel concept is basically an underground passage with entrance and exit at both ends. At first, tunnels were used for mining, but as technology advanced, transportation routes such as railroads, roads, and waterways became more important. This helps shorten the distance traveled. Tunnels are now being built all over the world, and the design requires careful planning.

There have been numerous trends and areas of research in tunnel architecture, and there has been considerable growth in recent times. The construction of tunnels, whether for transportation or water management, must take into account the type of terrain, structural integrity and safety standards.

Various case studies at various stage construction projects use the empirical method of tunnel design as well as an approach to assess rock quality and design supporting systems for excavations. (1) Several official classification systems for rocks, such as the Terzaghi Quality Index (RQD) and related methods like RMR or GSI (2). All displacement values and the thickness of the plastic zone are not properly calculated by the empirical method. To determine these factors numerically, the researchers proposed using them. (3)

In the early 1960s, numerical modeling was introduced to facilitate tunnel construction and underground mining. (4) In geotechnical projects, this approach involves the use of computer simulations and analysis of rock/soil/structure behavior. The use of numerical techniques enables engineers to comprehend intricate interactions, anticipate motion, determine stability levels and design optimization. Numerical modeling has become an important tool in modern geotechnical engineering, enabling more accurate and better decisions to be made during construction projects.

Numerical modeling for the analysis of tunnel and excavation was among the many developed in 20th century. These methods fall into two main categories: continuum and discontinuum models. (3).

The complexities of design and analysis are discussed in various types presented in this paper. Analysis of rock layers using empirical and numerical methods.

II. Tunnel Design

In today's world, tunneling has become a popular solution for solving design problems in cities with old pathways or obstacles, as well as in natural areas like mountains or underwater channels. This trend has greatly influenced recent advancements in tunneling technology. A multitude of crucial considerations come into play when planning a tunneling project. These considerations, which include environmental and factors, guide the optimal construction of tunnels in various locations (Kusakabe et al., 1999). (5-6) The main points are: -

1. Geotechnical and hydrogeological properties, the environmental condition of soil/rock layers.
2. Effects of tunnel construction on underground facilities and surfaces such as streets and buildings.
3. Possible availability of surface traffic for all vehicles or traffic management.
4. Financial aspects, technical requirements and the construction schedule are key factors to consider when planning a tunnel project.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology used to conduct this study explained in subsequent sections: -

- A topographical/Geological map was utilized to study the tunnel's layout and surroundings.
- To study the Field investigations was carried out to gather discontinuity parameters and collect samples for subsequent laboratory testing.
- Determining the shape and size of the tunnel will be based on both ground conditions and economic considerations.
- Design support for rock classification will be provided through empirical approaches.
- Representative models will be developed for numerical analysis in Phase2.0.
- These models will be run under specified conditions to determine total displacement, forces, and plastic zone thickness.

IV. GEOLOGY CONDITION

The geological setting of the area consists of Deccan Trap basalt flows (ranging from upper Cretaceous to lower Eocene age). These basalts are capped by lateritic soil and covered by alluvium with varying laminated thickness (1m to 6m). The Deccan trap flow overlays earlier formations, filling uneven pre-trapping topography. The Deccan trap streams are categorized into two main groups based on field studies.: compact and amygdaloid/vesicular basalt. Amygdaloid basalt is enriched in secondary minerals like zeolite and silica. It occurs both as the upper/lower part of thick, compact basalt flows and as independent flows throughout their thickness The general stratification of the basalt flows in the area includes:

- Amygdaloidal–Vesicular Trap basalt
- Massive Compact basalt
- Red bole bed
- Amygdaloidal–Vesicular basalt

The orientation joints set, faults plane, variation in lithology, lithological contact and shear zones along VMEH are encountered with varying characteristics traversing amygdaloidal rocks and massive basalt rock for central line of Twin Tunnel.

There is no Shear zone/ Weak zone observed along tunnel alignment. There is no active fault plain along tunnel alignment and tunnel area.

Figure.1: The geological map of India showing the Deccan traps

V. LABORATORY TEST

The laboratory testing was aimed to obtaining various engineering properties of rock from different layers. The summary of tests is important to have a very good information of rock mass behaviour characteristics beforehand to optimize construction activities and to know the lithological contacts and weathering status of intact rock of the site. Field studies, laboratory tests, and technical geological and geotechnical parameters were employed to determine the rock mass and determine appropriate support measures.

Table 1:- Rock properties from Lab Test

Lab Test	Rock Type-01	Rock Type-02
UCS	72.57	68.12

Lab Test	Rock Type-01	Rock Type-02
Unit Weight	24.00	24.00
Young Modulus	29954	22960
Poisson Ratio	0.23	0.22

VI. ROCK MASS RATING

The Bieniawski Rock Mass Rating (RMR) system developed in 1979 is important for evaluating rock mass conditions during mining and tunneling operations (2) It works with an empirical approach using surface geological data for fast and cost-effective evaluation. System parameters, including UCS, RQD and discontinuity spacing and conditions can be easily determined both in the laboratory and in the field, based on past field experience that informs current assessments. The Indian Standards incorporates parameters that have been modified, such as groundwater conditions and the absence of discontinuity orientation, to ensure relevance in various contexts. On-site implementation requires careful study of relevant parameters during site visits and laboratory testing of core samples. The points obtained as a result contribute to the total RMR values, which makes it possible to give comprehensive technical assessments of the suitability of a rock strata for various projects.

Table 2:- RMR Calculation in rock along the alignment of Tunnel

Rock Mass Unit	Rock Type-01	Rock Type-02
UCS	7.00	4.00
RQD	8.00	3.00
Spacing	15.00	10.00
Roughness	25.00	15.00
Groundwater Conditions	7.00	7.00
Orientation Adjustment	-7.00	-7.00
RMR Rating	55.00	25.00
Rock Class	Fair Rock (Class-III)	Poor Rock (Class-IV)
Q-Value	3.39	0.37

VII. SHAPE OF TUNNEL

The tunnel's geometry is a crucial component of its design. When designing a road tunnel, the primary objective is to facilitate safe traffic flow while minimizing costs. The tunnel's geometric characteristics, including cross-section, gradients, and curvature, significantly impact traffic safety. Typically, a tunnel should adhere to the same geometric standards as the adjoining open-air carriageways.

The tunnel’s cross-section primarily depends on the projected traffic volume and the ventilation system (if any), the area’s geology, and the need for pedestrian traffic, especially in urban settings. The section that is most economical to select should be determined by the anticipated geotechnical conditions, traffic volumes and operational demands. Based on future traffic forecasts and the number and width of footpaths, sidewalks (including wide ones that are not required for motor vehicles), curbs or drains – the final width is determined by using the necessary number of traffic lanes.

The necessary area for installing electromechanical and ventilation systems will be allocated within the standard cross sections. To achieve this, input from the electromechanical and ventilation designer will be consider. All requirements related to these installations, including cables, ventilation, lighting, CCTV, traffic signs, water supply pipes, emergency telephones, and hydrants, will be accommodated within the tunnel profile without violating the clearance profile.

The clearance profile height will be designed with 5.50m according to standard code and the width of the clearance profile will be designed according to standard code. The carriageway of tunnel is given below table: -

Table 3:- Details of Tunnel Carriageway of Tunnel

Description	Width	Total Width
Lane Width	3.750 m	-
No. of Lanes	4 Nos.	15.00 m
Paved Shoulder	3.000 m	3.00 m
Edge Strip	0.750 m	0.750 m
Total Width		18.75 m

Table 4:- Tunnel Dimension

Description	Size
Width	24.595 m
Height	11.700m
Radius-01	19.000m
Radius-02	6.125m
Radius-03	5.652m

Figure.2: Design Shape & Geometry of Tunnel

VIII. EMPIRICAL METHOD

The design methods for empirical support in the stability of underground projects aim to incorporate the knowledge acquired from similar projects executed under comparable conditions. These methods are characterized by their ability to categorize a broad spectrum of rock mass quality and pair each category with various support measures. Bolts, steel ribs or lattice girders, and sprayed concrete are recommended as primary support elements by these empirical methods. Furthermore, these support measures consider the stages of excavation and the stresses that arise. A typical empirical method is detailed below: -

Preliminary Rock Support Design by Empirical Method

The rock support components include a) an initial layer of sprayed concrete, b) rock bolts, c) steel ribs or lattice girder, d) tie rods, e) lagging, and f) backfill concrete. The appropriate combination of these supports is determined by referring to standard geotechnical charts. Barton et al. (1974) introduced a parameter known as the Equivalent Dimension, D_e , of the excavation. (7).

In the creation of empirical support design methods for underground project stability, experiences from similar projects in similar conditions are incorporated. The key feature of these methods is the segmentation of a wider range of rock mass quality, pairing each category with different support measures. Bolts, steel ribs or trusses, and precast concrete are recommended as primary support elements in these empirical methods. Additionally, these support measures account for the excavation stages and the stresses that develop. A typical empirical method is outlined below: -

Preliminary Rock Support Design Using Empirical Method

The components of rock support are a) a single layer of precast concrete, b) rock bolts, c) steel ribs or truss, d) tie rods, e) lagging, and f) backfill concrete. The appropriate combination of these supports is determined by referring to standard geotechnical charts. Barton et al. defined a parameter for excavation known as the Equivalent Dimension, D_e . (7).

Recommended Support System

1. CLASS-III: - Proposed Support
 - a) 25MM Dia. 6000mm long 1750mm spacing.
 - b) 175mm thick Fiber reinforced sprayed concrete.
 - c) 100mm thick Fiber reinforced sprayed concrete.
2. CLASS-IV: - Proposed Support
 - a) 25MM Dia. 6000mm long 1000mm spacing.
 - b) Sprayed Concrete 100mm thick with 100mm X 100mm X 6mm wire mesh.
 - c) 200mm with lattice girder Fiber reinforced Sprayed Concrete.
 - d) 300mm thick cast-in-situ lining.

IX. NUMERICAL METHODS

The rock experiences stresses at depth that are a result of the upper layers' mass and also the stresses associated with their tectonic origin. The significance induced stresses in surface mining design lies within the directions and magnitudes of the stresses, which can lead to instability when stress levels exceed rock strength. implications for excavation behavior. During the last three decades, many researchers have incorporated numerical analyzes geotechnical projects (8-9).

Table 5:- Input Parameter for Numerical Analysis

Parameters	Unit	Fair Rock (Class-III)	Poor Rock (Class-IV)
RMR Range		41-60	21-40

Parameters	Unit	Fair Rock (Class-III)	Poor Rock (Class-IV)
RMR Considered		55.00	35.00
GSI	-	50.00	30.00
UCS	Mpa	72.57	68.12
Unit Weight	KN/m ³	24.00	24.00
Tunnel Depth	m	50.00	50.00
mi	-	24	24
Young Modulus	Mpa	29954	22960
Poisson Ratio		0.23	0.22
Disturbance Factor,D		D-0.0	D-0.0
Cohesion (C)	Mpa	0.47	0.34
Friction Angle (Phi)	Deg.	60.88	57.33
Tensile Strength	MPa	0.00	0.00
Modulus of deformation	MPa	5480.40	1868.56
Disturbance Factor, D		D-0.4	D-0.4
Cohesion (C)	Mpa	0.38	0.27
Friction Angle (Phi)	Deg.	57.54	52.72
Tensile Strength	MPa	0.00	0.00
Modulus of deformation	MPa	3028.83	1129.98

FEM phase 2 software is used for FEM analysis and support validation as suggested above. It is advisable to excavate the tunnel in different sections, in this case the following sections are realized at a certain distance behind the previous section. Rock bolts and concrete are used after each section of excavation to fix the contours of the tunnel.

Numerical analysis is done taking the rock material as plastic. The analysis is performed in nine steps. The nine steps are: -

1. Stage-01: - Initial Step
2. Stage-02: - Excavation and Initial Support Installation in Heading -01 (LHS)
3. Stage-03: - Excavation and Initial Support Installation in Heading -02 (LHS)
4. Stage-04: - Excavation and Initial Support Installation in Benching (LHS)
5. Stage-05: - Excavation and Initial Support Installation in Heading -01 (RHS)
6. Stage-06: - Excavation and Initial Support Installation in Heading -02 (RHS)
7. Stage-07: - Excavation and Initial Support Installation in Heading -01 (RHS)
8. Stage-08: - Final Lining Installation (LHS)
9. Stage-09: - Final Lining Installation (RHS)

The main input parameter of Phase2 was used under plastic conditions. We looked at the three triangular meshes used in the program to calculate stresses and strains. The thickness of the plastic zones and total displacements were determined for both Class III and IV conditions as shown in Table 7. Details of the bolts and concrete support properties are given in Table 6 below.

Table 6:- Support Properties

Bolt Properties	
Type	Fully Bonded
Diameter (mm)	25.00
Bolt Modulus (Mpa)	200000
Tensile Capacity (MN)	0.10
Tensile Capacity (Residual) (MN)	0.01
Out Plane Spacing (m)	1.75

Sprayed Concrete Properties	
Young Modulus (Mpa)	31622.8
Poisson Ratio	0.175
Compressive Strength (Mpa)	40.00
Tensile Strength (Mpa)	4.42

The models were analysed in class III and IV. The maximum displacement was observed between 9.75 and 18.10 mm in Class IV and the plastic zone is high in Class IV stones. Details of the results of the numerical analyses are included in Table 7.

During the analysis in Class-III and Class-IV rock condition, the software interpreted the zone of deformation. This empirical method is then supported by the model which provides it for verification purposes. The models of numerical analysis in Class-III and Class-IV are given below.

Total Displacement in Class-IV in After Initial Support is 18.01mm

Total Displacement in Class-IV in Final lining 18.01mm

Plastic Thickness in Class-IV is 13.096m

Total Displacement in Class-III in After Initial Support is 6.30mm

Total Displacement in Class-III in Final lining is 6.30mm

Plastic Thickness in Class-III is 12.084m

X. SUPPORT CAPACITY

Engineers can use load capacity charts to determine the factor of safety for provided supports such as sprayed concrete and linings. For a given safety factor, the power envelope curves show the axial force, moment state and displacement. After that, the axial forces, moments and shear values of the supplied supports are compared with the bearing capacity limits. If the calculated line values fall within the envelope, their confidence factor is greater than the envelope value. If the calculated values fall below the safety measurement factor, the safety level is higher than the actual value.

Initial Support Capacity Curve in Class-III rock

Final Support Capacity Curve in Class-III rock

Initial Support Capacity Curve in Class-IV rock

Final Support Capacity Curve in Class-IV rock

Table 7:- Numerical Analysis Result Summary

Sl. No.	Description	Unit	Class-IV Values			Class-III Values		
			LHS Tube	RHS Tube	No. of Yield Element (Nos)	LHS Tube	RHS Tube	No. of Yield Element (Nos)
1	Displacements							
a)	Stage-2	mm	9.75	0.75	118.00	3.30	0.30	54.00
b)	Stage-3	mm	14.30	0.975	214.00	5.60	0.70	135.00
c)	Stage-4	mm	18.10	0.95	192.00	6.65	0.35	120.00
d)	Stage-5	mm	18.10	9.50	312.00	6.30	3.85	178.00
e)	Stage-6	mm	18.10	16.20	371.00	6.30	0.70	216.00

Sl. No.	Description	Unit	Class-IV Values			Class-III Values		
			LHS Tube	RHS Tube	No. of Yield Element (Nos)	LHS Tube	RHS Tube	No. of Yield Element (Nos)
f)	Stage-7	mm	18.10	18.1	354.00	6.30	6.30	200.00
g)	Stage-8	mm	18.10	18.10	354.00	6.30	6.30	200.00
h)	Stage-9)	mm	18.10	18.10	354.00	6.30	6.30	200.00
2	Thickness of Plastic Zone	m	13.096	12.554	-	11.963	12.084	-

XI. CONCLUSION

In this study, we utilized the numerical modeling tool phase2 to validate the support recommendations suggested by empirical methods. The rock masses were categorized as ranging from good to poor according to RMR system and from fair to very poor based on the Q-system from given engineering properties of rock. In this study, we designing the shape and geometry of tunnels to ensure safety within specific strata (Class-III & Class-IV rock). Our observations reveal that when the rock quality is good, less support is necessary, whereas poor-quality rock demands more substantial support.

XII. References

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